

IMPROVING THE ACCOUNTING AND CONTROL OF EXTRA BUDGETARIY FUNDS

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Abstract. *This article compares important information on the topic of improving the accounting and control of extrabudgetary funds and makes proposals for the redistribution of funds. This article provides important information on the subject of accounting and control of extrabudgetary funds in the correction and control of financial calculations. This article describes how funds are used, their correct calculation, preventive measures and theoretical foundations. It will be useful for those operating in the field of financial control and advanced funds control.*

Keywords: *improvement, calculation, funds, control, off-budget, purpose, tasks, functions, subject, objects.*

Budgeting and managing external funds is essential for organizations to maintain financial stability and sustainability. By keeping records of expenses, income, and investments, organizations can make confident financial decisions. This includes monitoring and controlling external funds, as well as analyzing financial statements, conducting audits, and implementing internal controls to prevent fraud and mismanagement. Incorporating technology such as financial management software can simplify the process of budgeting and monitoring external funds. It helps organizations increase efficiency, accuracy and transparency in their financial transactions. In addition, regularly reviewing and updating budgeting and monitoring processes can help organizations adapt to changing economic conditions and ensure long-term financial success.

In our country, in the future, planning the state budget for the medium term, focusing on the result when allocating funds to the budget, strengthening the revenue part of local budgets in the Development Strategy for 2022-2026, budgets of different levels while maintaining the social orientation of state budget expenditures tasks such as ensuring proportionality are envisaged.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev referring to the tax-budget policy, says: “Strict adherence to the tax-budget policy, fulfillment of the state’s social obligations, the amount of wages, pensions, allowances and scholarships, financing of large investment projects and the strengthening country’s defense capabilities – these are the most important tasks. The Ministry of Finance is currently creating conditions for the full formation of market relations in front of the tax system of our country, as well as providing the state budget with funds and supporting priority economic activities through tax support”.

Effective budgeting and management of external funds can be achieved through proper accounting and full control. Here are some basic steps to consider:

1. Setting clear and realistic financial goals and objectives.
2. Prepare a detailed budget reflecting expected income and expenses.
3. Regular monitoring and tracking all financial transactions to ensure accuracy.
4. Implementation of internal controls to protect against fraud and misuse of funds.
5. Conducting regular audits to assess financial performance and regulatory compliance.
6. Developing contingency plans to deal with unexpected events or financial problems.

7. Seeking professional recommendation or training to improve financial management skills.

8. Continuing review and adjusting budget and accounting processes to optimize efficiency and effectiveness.

By following these steps, organizations can improve their ability to effectively manage external funds and maintain financial stability.

In the conditions of the market economy, proper accounting in budget organizations leads to the rational use of state budget revenues. For this reason, it is necessary to carry out scientific research and studies on this topic. The budget organization as stated in Article 4 of the Budget Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan is defined as follows: “Budget organization is a non-profit organization established by the decision of the state authorities in order to implement state functions and maintained at the expense of the State budget. The terms of financing of budget organizations and the procedure for keeping budget accounts are determined by budget legislation.”

Section I of the “Instructions on Accounting in Budget Organizations” states how to organize accounting in budget organizations: “Budget organizations should organize accounting for budget and extra-budget. They are organized in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Accounting”, this Instruction and other regulatory legal documents.”

According to the researches, a number of scientific studies aimed at adapting the methodology of budget execution calculation and reporting, as well as control to international standards, have been carried out in the public sector of the countries of the world. In these studies, issues such as the budget system and its management, methods and directions for organizing the budget execution account, ensuring the openness of information on the execution of the state budget and increasing accountability, and improving the information supply of the budget report have been solved. Also, the role of the accounting information system in ensuring the effective use of funds in organizations in the public sectors, issues of strengthening, ensuring transparency of information, forming aggregate information were researched as a separate direction. At this point, it is necessary to note that in the conducted researches, the issues of budget execution accounting and reporting have been developed, as well as directions for increasing the role of accounting in the formation of budget execution.

According to Muhammadyaqub Ostanakulov, the budget organization is entrusted with this. It is a state organization that is supposed to allocate funds from the state budget for the implementation of its activities related to the performance of tasks and is considered the main source of financing of these funds. Budget organizations include state organizations, higher education institutions, research institutes, schools, boarding schools, colleges, lyceums, hospitals, polyclinics, kindergartens, nurseries, etc.

Among the economists of our republic, A.Q. Ibrohimov, S.U.Mehmonov, M.Ostonakulov, A.J.Toychiyev, Sh.V.Ganiyev, B.Q.Khamdamov’s works cover accounting, economic analysis and audit, budget accounting, reporting and its theoretical issues.

To improve the accounting and control of extra-budgetary funds, monitoring of funds in large accounts and registration of accounts are key indicators. This will help to ensure the correct calculation and indicators, the restructuring of funds and the operation of funds selected by the state budget with additional visits. These indicators include determining the forms of payment of funds, information on funds. And for control, the need to list all the initial basic funds and costs,

diagnose other conditions and additional payment costs and adjust and check them on the monitor is described.

The state budget is created on the basis of financial provision of budget organizations and recipients of funds from the budget, as well as financing of state expenses. According to the report of the International Monetary Fund, budget expenditures in developed countries are equal to 40% of the gross domestic product, and it is noted that public sector organizations are considered the main employer in terms of providing employment. In global practice, financing of organizations in the public sector comes from the state budget and extrabudgetary funds. Targeted spending of budget and extrabudgetary funds in budget organizations is directly related to the effective organization of their accounts and the transparency of financial reporting indicators. Therefore, in most countries of the world, special attention is paid to the development of budget execution accounting and reporting in accordance with the requirements of international accounting standards in the public sector.

REFERENCES

1. Budget Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2014.
2. Mirziyoyev Sh. “Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should be the daily rule of every leader’s activity.” T: “Uzbekistan”-20172.
3. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017 “On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan” Decision No. PF-4947 of February 7.
4. Instruction “On accounting in budget organizations” Uz.R AV. <http://www.lex.uz> was registered on December 22, 2010 with number 2169;
5. M. Ostanakulov. Accounting in budget organizations. The second edition (reworked and supplemented).-Tashkent, “Iktisodiyot-moliya”, 2009, 428 p.
6. Mehmonov S.U., Kuliboyev A.Sh. Account of extra-budgetary funds of budget organizations. Study guide, “Economics and finance 2018. 186 p.